

Value quiz clocks.

This is the value add time travelling clock:

This is the value add space travelling clock:

Note: These are value add, value subtract, value multiply, and value divide space travelling clocks and time travelling clocks. These clocks can come in many shapes and forms that effectively follow one rule for either of the space clock or time clock, and that is time travelling clocks are mono-time based, therefore no straight parts to the clock, just the one time curve and the other one time curve to the time clock, and for the space travelling clock there are no curved parts to the clock, which again means that is solely mono-space based, which means lines, squares, and hexagonal gears. These clocks can be either exist as mono-quantitative, mono-qualitative, or either qualitative or quantitative depending on what is being added, subtracted, divided, or multiplied. There can even exist a fusion space-time clock which fuses space and time together.